

EXPLORING AND HIGHLIGHTING USEFUL DATASETS AND TOOLS FOR POTENTIAL DAM REMOVAL HOTSPOTS

REPORT

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Authorship

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Executive summary

This work was carried out by the authors at the request of the Open Rivers Programme (ORP). The European Open Rivers Programme is a Dutch grant-giving organisation dedicated to restoring rivers. The programme offers grants to support projects that lead to the removal of small dams and the restoration of river flow and biodiversity. The programme is funded by Arcadia. This report was written by the authors but does not represent the views of ORP. The authors are not responsible for the production of the input datasets and tools. Access to the datasets and tools was provided by ORP, which facilitated meetings with the data providers. The results presented in this report assume the data is correct, as no validation or correction procedures were undertaken. The views expressed in this report resulted from discussions between the authors and ORP, according to the objectives determined by ORP.

Context and Background: The ORP aims to restore natural river flows by removing obsolete dams and barriers, thereby enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services. This study focuses on interpreting available datasets and tools to assist ORP in identifying potential "dam removal hotspots" to prioritise efforts and resources effectively.

Methodology: The authors explored four datasets and tools provided by ORP. This involved detailed analysis and mapping of the data, as well as synthesising the information into a coherent summary. Meetings with data providers facilitated a deeper understanding of the datasets and their potential applications.

Key Findings: The analysis identified several key areas where dam removal could significantly impact river restoration. Each dataset and tool provided unique insights, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of potential hotspots.

Implications and Recommendations: The findings suggest that targeted dam removals in identified areas could maximise ecological benefits. Recommendations include refining the datasets and tools to improve accuracy and usability, as well as conducting field validations to confirm the data insights.

Future Work: Further research could involve developing advanced modelling techniques to predict the ecological outcomes of dam removals. Additionally, expanding the datasets to include more variables and conducting long-term monitoring post-dam removal would provide valuable feedback for the ORP.

The goals of this exercise were to:

- Explore the four datasets and tools provided by ORP
- Identify their potential use in defining "dam removal hotspots" by ORP
- Map the outcomes of each dataset and tool
- Produce a summary of each dataset and tool in the form of a presentation
- Assist ORP in interpreting the outputs of the individual datasets and tools
- Propose a way to better leverage the datasets and tools to help ORP identify "dam removal hotspots"
- Discuss the outcomes with ORP and provide a final exercise output

Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS)

Responsible organisation

European Open Rivers Programme

Garcia de Leaniz, C., Jones, J., Börger, L. (2021). Ranking of Europe's River Basins for Dam Removal: an evidence-based approach. Swansea University.

Contacts

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Professor Luca Börger (l.borger@swansea.ac.uk)

Objectives

The DAMROS methodology was developed to assist the ORP in selecting projects in catchments with a high potential for restoring biodiversity, ensuring optimal returns for the money spent. This methodology provides a scoring mechanism to evaluate the attractiveness of river catchments for dam removal, based on 10 metrics that capture four crucial aspects of dam removal.

Data from these metrics were used to score 211,075 individual Surface Water Bodies (SWBs), offering the highest spatial resolution. Additionally, data was aggregated into 172 River Basin Districts (RBDs) and further into countries, covering the three most relevant spatial scales for management. The total area encompasses 1,699,234 kilometres of river length across 35 countries, including both natural and heavily modified water bodies.

To ensure accuracy and avoid bias, each original metric was scaled from 0 to 1, ensuring equal weighting in the final score. The methodology explicitly considered the quality and completeness of the data, the redundancy and complementarity of different metrics, and the robustness of the resulting lists to the influence of individual metrics. Utilising publicly available data helped ensure transparency and repeatability of the scores.

Key parameters and attributes

The index is based on 10 metrics that take into account (1) the extent of fragmentation, (2) river quality and biodiversity, (3) governance and support for dam removal, and (4) futureproofing, based on predicted changes in water flow caused by climate change (Table 1).

Table 1. Criteria and metrics used in the DAMROS scoring system for ranking the suitability of European river basins for dam removal.

DAMROS Criteria and Metric	Original metric	High score	Low score	Data Source	Rationale for inclusion
A. Fragmentation					
1. Barrier density	No. barriers/km	<mean	≥mean	1	Dam removal is more likely to be effective in the least fragmented basins because larger areas of river can be made free-flowing. It is likely to be more cost-effective to restore river continuity in areas of lower fragmentation.
2. Extent of barriers under-reporting	Reporting bias	0%	100%	1	
3. QE2-2 – River continuity conditions	1-5	1	5	2	
B. Biodiversity and River Quality					
4. Chemical status	1-5	1	5	2	The four metrics combined were considered to provide a strong measure of the ecological value of a river.
5. Ecological status	1-5	1	5	2	
6. Biodiversity value (mean BQE-1)	1-5	1	5	2	
7. Included in Protected area	Y/N	Yes	No	3	

DAMROS Criteria and Metric	Original metric	High score	Low score	Data Source	Rationale for inclusion
C. Governance & Support for dam removal					
8. Barriers flagged as pressure in RBMP (P4-2)	Y/N	Yes	No	2	The two metrics help to provide a broad indication of the degree to which dam removal is recognised and supported.
9. Support for dam removal	No. removals	=ref value	<ref value	4	
D. Future-proofing					
10. Water stress and future flows	% flow change	decrease	increase	5	Barrier impacts are likely to increase in places where river flows decrease and vice versa. This means that barrier removals will be most beneficial in places where connectivity is most at risk due to droughts and reduced river flows.

Table 2. Metrics used in the different DAMROS indices and sample sizes.

DAMROS Criteria and Metric	SWBs with data	RBD with data	DAMROS 10	DAMROS 7	DAMROS 5	DAMROS 4
A. Fragmentation						
1. Barrier density	209,796	172	Y	Y	Y	Y
2. Quality of existing barrier data	182,999	133	Y	Y	Y	Y
3. QE2-2 - River continuity conditions	11,637	46	Y	N	N	N

DAMROS Criteria and Metric	SWBs with data	RBD with data	DAMROS 10	DAMROS 7	DAMROS 5	DAMROS 4
B. Biodiversity & River quality						
4. Chemical Status	27,038	128	Y	Y	N	N
5. Ecological Status	29,374	133	Y	Y	N	N
6. Biodiversity value (mean BQE-1)	9,897	81	Y	Y	N	N
7. Included in a Protected area	138,478	170	Y	Y	Y	Y
C. Governance & Support for dam removal						
8. Barriers as pressure in RBMP (P4-2)	138,472	165	Y	N	Y	N
9. Support for dam removal	70,247	66	Y	N	N	N
D. Future-proofing						
10. Water stress & future flows	184,505	163	Y	Y	Y	Y

Input datasets

- Belletti, B., Garcia de Leaniz, C., Jones, J., Bizzi, S., Börger, L., Segura, G., et al. (2020). More than one million barriers fragment Europe's rivers. *Nature* 588, 436-441.
- <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/wise-wfd-4>
- <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-13>
- <https://damremoval.eu/dam-removal-map-europe/>
- Alfieri, L., Feyen, L., Dottori, F., Mentaschi, L., Cammalleri, C., Bisselink, B., De Roo, A. (2020). Hazards: floods, drought and water resources. European Commission, Joint Research Centre.

Maps

Figure 1 – Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS 4) per River Basin District.

Figure 2 – Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS 4) per Surface Water Body.

Figure 3 – Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS 5) per River Basin District.

Figure 4 – Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS 5) per Surface Water Body.

Figure 5 – Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS 5) per River Basin District.

Figure 6 – Dam Removal Opportunity Score (DAMROS 10) per Surface Water Body.

Trans-European Swimways Network

Responsible organisation

Global Swimways

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Objectives

Swimways are “rivers and their associated ecosystems that support the entire migration routes of freshwater fishes”. The Trans-European Swimways Programme aims to support the recovery of migratory freshwater fishes in Europe through coordinated policy and advocacy, capacity building, and field actions at critical locations.

Goal: To contribute to the recovery of migratory freshwater fishes by restoring Swimways across Europe.

Purpose: To reduce the rate of decline of migratory freshwater fishes in Europe through the identification and protection of Swimways of European Importance.

Key parameters and attributes

For this analysis, only freshwater fish species classified as full migrants according to the IUCN’s definition (“a substantial proportion of the global or regional population makes regular or seasonal cyclical movements beyond the breeding range, with predictable timing and destinations”) were used. This definition is consistent with those proposed by other fish experts (Deinet et al. 2020), and it includes both diadromous (migrating between freshwater and marine waters) and potamodromous (restricted to freshwater habitats) fish species. Within the diadromous fish species, there are anadromous (travel from the sea to spawn in freshwater), catadromous (travel from freshwater to spawn in the sea), estuarine (travelling from sea or freshwater to brackish water to spawn), and amphidromous (migrate either direction between saltwater and freshwater, but not for breeding purposes) species. The basis of this assessment is the European Red List of Freshwater Fishes (Freyhof

and Brooks, 2011). The migratory status was classified based on IUCN Red List factsheets, the Handbook of European Freshwater Fishes (Kottelat & Freyhof, 2007) and consultation with other sources and experts. Species with extant or possibly extant ranges, species with native origin, or species that had been reintroduced were selected. Of the 538 European freshwater species in the Swimways dataset, 136 were considered to be migratory: 56 of them are anadromous, 10 catadromous, 2 estuarine, and 68 potamodromous. 96 of the 136 European migratory freshwater fish occur in the European Union. Species for which distribution data are absent and those currently being assessed for the IUCN Red List were removed, resulting in a final dataset of 665 species. To aid computational processing, only river segments with long-term average discharges exceeding $10 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ were included in the analysis. Within the HydroRIVERS dataset, river segments are attributed to basins, with the entire network of a basin identified here as the “main river”. For each river segment, three biological metrics were quantified: (1) species richness, (2) the number of threatened species, and (3) the number of endemic species (for which there is consistent data). Segment species richness was defined as the number of species whose ranges overlapped with each segment. This segment species pool was further classified based on its threat status and endemism. The number of threatened species was defined as the number of species in a segment classified as critically endangered, endangered, or vulnerable based on their Red List assessments. Endemic species were those whose ranges were confined to a single basin, with basin extents mapped using Level 4 HydroBASINS (median area: 55,927 km²). Case study regions were selected by identifying areas where river segments had consistently high species richness ($n = 2$), threatened species ($n = 1$), or the highest number of endemic species ($n = 1$).

Criteria were proposed at three different levels:

- Global:
 - Globally threatened (GT) migratory freshwater species, according to the Red List from the IUCN.
- European:
 - European threatened (ET) migratory freshwater species, according to the Red List from the IUCN.
 - Migratory freshwater fishes listed in the Bern Convention (BC).

- Subregional (EU level):

- European Union 28 threatened (EUT) migratory freshwater fishes.
- Migratory freshwater fishes listed in the Annexes of the EU Habitat Directives (HD).

Data was obtained from the IUCN and UNEP-WCMC regarding the status of the migratory freshwater species according to the threatened red list at the 3 different levels and combined with the data from the list of the Bern Convention and Habitat Directive. After comparing taxonomic changes and applying the IUCN Red List criteria, 92 migratory freshwater fish species were identified matching the European Swimways criteria.

To classify the data, the focus was on the richness of migratory fish species found in the European River stretches. Within the 5 mentioned categories (GT, ET, BC, EUT and HD), two potential thresholds for river sections were examined: a more restrictive top 10% and a more relaxed top 20% based on their species richness. This approach results in excluding 90% or 80% of the river sections, respectively.

References

- Deinet, S., Scott-Gatty, K., Rotton, H., Twardek, W. M., Marconi, V., McRae, L., Baumgartner, L. J., Brink, K., Claussen, J. E., Cooke, S. J., Darwall, W., Eriksson, B. K., Garcia de Leaniz, C., Hogan, Z., Royte, J., Silva, L. G. M., Thieme, M. L., Tickner, D., Waldman, J., ... Berkhuyzen, A. (2020). The Living Planet Index (LPI) for migratory freshwater fish: Technical Report. World Fish Migration Foundation. https://worldfishmigrationfoundation.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/LPI_report_2020.pdf
- Freyhof, J., & Brooks, E. (2011). European red list of freshwater fishes.
- Kottelat, M., & Freyhof, J. (2007). Handbook of European freshwater fishes (Vol. 13). Cornol, Switzerland: Publications Kottelat.

Input datasets

The river network used is HydroRIVERS (HydroRIVERS data was used as part of the HydroBASINS (Lehner and Grill, 2013) data that is also used in the IUCN freshwater species assessment process.

Species data were derived from the IUCN Red List database (IUCN, 2020). We identified 92 migratory freshwater fish species to consider in the European Swimways criteria.

Data on large dams was collected from the GOODD (Mulligan et al., 2020) and GrAND (Lehner et al., 2011) datasets.

– Lehner, B. and Grill, G. (2013). Global river hydrography and network routing: baseline data and new approaches to study the world’s large river systems. *Hydrological Processes*, 27(15): 2171–2186.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.9740>

– Garner, B. A., Hoban, S., & Luikart, G. (2020). IUCN Red List and the value of integrating genetics. *Conservation Genetics*, 21(5), 795-801.

–Mulligan, M., van Soesbergen, A., & Sáenz, L. (2020). GOODD, a global dataset of more than 38,000 georeferenced dams. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), 31.

–Lehner, B., Liermann, C. R., Revenga, C., Vörösmarty, C., Fekete, B., Crouzet, P., ... & Robertson, J. C. (2011). Global reservoir and dam (GrAND) database. Technical Documentation, Version 1, 1-14.

Maps

72% of the river stretches in Europe considered in the SEI report are covered by the 20% threshold, and 46% by the 10% level of the Swimways of European Importance. 21% would be globally important, 44% would be regionally important, and only 6% or 10% would be sub-regionally important at the 20% and 10% levels, respectively.

Figure 7 – Swimways of European Importance (SEI) for migratory freshwater fish species in European rivers identified using a 20% threshold (Level of importance: Global- burgundy; Regional- orange; Sub-regional- yellow). The river network used is HydroRIVERS, which is part of the HydroBASINS network (Lehner and Grill, 2013).

Figure 8 – Swimways of European Importance (SEI) for migratory freshwater fish species in European rivers identified using a 20% threshold (Level of importance: Global- burgundy; Regional- orange; Sub-regional- yellow). Large dams (green dots) were collected from the GOODD (Mulligan et al., 2020) and GrAND (Lehner et al., 2011) datasets. The river network used is HydroRIVERS, which is part of the HydroBASINS network (Lehner and Grill, 2013).

TNC's River Basin Prioritization Tool

Responsible organization

The Nature Conservancy

The tool was produced by Confluvio Consulting Inc

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The tool can be accessed through the following link: <https://tnc-app-dd8a4.web.app/>

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Objectives

To enhance conservation outcomes for both ecosystems and communities across Europe, The Nature Conservancy (TNC) Europe Freshwater team is currently engaged in a comprehensive geographic prioritisation assessment. This assessment aims to pinpoint key locations outside of their existing areas of focus where freshwater conservation initiatives can be effectively implemented.

Confluvio has developed a specialised prioritisation tool for TNC, streamlining the geographic prioritisation process. The tool's framework aligns with the four core strategic pillars of the TNC Europe Freshwater Team: Avoidance, Protection, Restoration, and Resilience. Within each pillar, the analysis

delves into a) the richness of freshwater biodiversity and ecosystem diversity in Europe, b) the current status of natural systems, and c) anticipated future threats.

By integrating results from these pillar-specific analyses, the tool generates a comprehensive prioritisation assessment for Europe as a whole. The integration of this tool into TNC's workflow will empower the organisation to pinpoint priority areas across Europe that align with its strategic objectives, thereby maximising positive outcomes for both nature and communities.

Key parameters and attributes

- a) Freshwater biodiversity and freshwater ecosystem diversity in Europe
- b) The current state of natural systems
- c) Future threats

Certain layers may have some redundancy with each other. Incorporating layers with redundancy can lead to "double counting," potentially accentuating specific phenomena represented by the data layers. While this emphasis might prove advantageous in scenarios where prioritisation focuses on a particular phenomenon, it could also be disadvantageous if the goal is to evenly consider multiple phenomena, inadvertently giving undue emphasis to one over the others. There is the option to prioritise layers through weighted overlay analysis. Within this framework, each group of metrics and individual layers can be assigned weights categorised as low, medium, or high, utilising the three-star options. Alternatively, users can set the weight to zero if necessary. Moreover, the direction of optimisation for each layer can be reversed.

Prioritisation scores are calculated using an aggregate weighted average:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

W - weighted average; n - number of layers to be averaged; X_i - layer attribute values to be averaged; w_i - weights (*i.e.*, the absolute number of stars) multiplied with the attribute value, X_i

ORP Hotspot Scenario

This scenario was produced with the assistance of the authors, but all the decisions were formally made by ORP according to their goals (date: 16/2/2024).

Restore Weighted Average

Biodiversity (3)

- ✓ Freshwater Species Rarity (1)
- ✓ Freshwater Species Diversity (1)
- ✓ Freshwater Species Diversity Threatened (1)
- ✓ Fish Species Diversity – All (3)
- ✓ Fish Species Diversity – Threatened (3)
- ✓ Freshwater Habitat Diversity (3)

Current State (2)

- ✓ Nitrogen Stream Concentration (1)
- ✓ Phosphorus Stream Concentration (1)
- ✓ Avg Probability of Failing Good Ecological Status (2)
- ✓ Human Modification Index (1)
- ✓ AMBER Barrier Density (3)
- ✓ Protected Areas (3)

Filter

Water Quality

- ✓ Avg Probability of Failing Good Ecological Status (<0.6)

Connectivity

- ✓ AMBER Barrier Density (<1)

Input datasets

HydroBASINS delineates watershed boundaries and sub-basins on a global scale (Lehner & Grill 2013). The sub-basin delineations within HydroBASINS follow a nested hierarchy, establishing a series of sub-

basins across various spatial scales. In this context, HydroBASINS level 10 serves as the primary scale for integrating data into the HydroSHEDS framework.

Main datasets:

– Lehner, B. and Grill, G. (2013). Global river hydrography and network routing: baseline data and new approaches to study the world’s large river systems. *Hydrological Processes*, 27(15): 2171–2186.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.9740>

– Article 17 Web Tool. 2022. Article 17 Web Tool. [online] Available at: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-bd/activities/reporting/article-17>>

-UCN Red List of Threatened Species spatial data. [online] Available at: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/>

Below is Table 3 with all the layers of information for the THC tool (Source - TNC Europe Freshwater Outcomes Prioritisation (TEFOP) Data Catalogue).

Table 3. TNC Prioritization Tool Layer List (Version 1.0). Source - TNC Europe Freshwater Outcomes Prioritization (TEFOP) Data Catalogue.

TNC Prioritization Tool Layer List (Version 1.0)				
(click hyperlinked ID to jump to individual information sheet)				
ID	Indicator Group	Layer Name	Sub-group	Field Name
100	Biodiversity	Freshwater Habitat Diversity	Habitat	bi_hb_ab
105	Biodiversity	Freshwater Species Rarity Weighted Richness Index	Rarity Weighted Richness Index	bi_raf_c
106	Biodiversity	Terrestrial Species Rarity Weighted Richness Index	Rarity Weighted Richness Index	bi_rat_c
110	Biodiversity	Freshwater Species Diversity – All	Freshwater Species	bi_an_ab
112	Biodiversity	Terrestrial Species Diversity – All	Terrestrial Species	bi_at_ab
115	Biodiversity	Freshwater Species Diversity – Threatened	Freshwater Species	bi_tn_ab
117	Biodiversity	Terrestrial Species Diversity – Threatened	Terrestrial Species	bi_tt_ab
120	Biodiversity	Freshwater Species Diversity – Endemic	Freshwater Species	bi_en_ab
122	Biodiversity	Terrestrial Species Diversity – Endemic	Terrestrial Species	bi_et_ab
125	Biodiversity	Freshwater Species Diversity - Decreasing Trend	Freshwater Species	bi_dn_ab
127	Biodiversity	Terrestrial Species Diversity - Decreasing Trend	Terrestrial Species	bi_dt_ab
150	Biodiversity	Fish Species Diversity	Fish Species	bi_af_ab
155	Biodiversity	Fish Species Diversity – Threatened	Fish Species	bi_tf_ab
160	Biodiversity	Fish Species Diversity – Endemic	Fish Species	bi_ef_ab
165	Biodiversity	Fish Species Diversity – Decreasing Trend	Fish Species	bi_df_ab
175	Biodiversity	Invasive Alien Species - Freshwater	Habitat	bi_iv_ix
180	Biodiversity	Bird Species Diversity	Bird Species	bi_ab_ab
185	Biodiversity	Threatened Bird Species Diversity	Bird Species	bi_tb_ab
190	Biodiversity	Freshwater Key Biodiversity Areas	Habitat	kb_fw_sp
210	Current State	Natural Discharge	Climate Baseline	d_m3_pyr
215	Current State	Aridity Potential	Climate Baseline	ar_ph_sa
217	Current State	Drought Frequency Probability	Climate Baseline	dr_fp_sa
220	Current State	Water Exploitation Index	Development Pressure	we_av_sa
222	Current State	Groundwater Depletion	Development Pressure	gw_pq_sa
223	Current State	Recharge Zone Habitats	Land Use / Cover	rw_pa_sp
224	Current State	Groundwater with Poor Chemical Status due to Agriculture	Water Quality	gw_pc_sa
225	Current State	Average Probability of Failing Good Ecological Status	Water Quality	ge_pf_sa
230	Current State	Erosion in Croplands	Water Quality	cl_cu_ty
235	Current State	Nitrogen Stream Concentration	Water Quality	n_sch_sa
240	Current State	Phosphorus Stream Concentration	Water Quality	p_sch_sa

Maps

Figure 9 – Overall prioritization assessment for European freshwater restoration, with Restore Weighted Average ranging from very low (light yellow) to very high (dark blue). Layers selected according to ORP Hotspot Scenario (16/2/2024) (listed above).

Filtered Prioritization Assessment for European Freshwater Restoration

Figure 10 – Overall prioritization assessment for European freshwater restoration, with Restore Weighted Average ranging from very low (light yellow) to very high (dark blue). Layers selected according to ORP Hotspot Scenario (16/2/2024) (listed above), filtered by Probability of Failing Good Ecological Status (<0.6) and AMBER Barrier Density (<1 per km).

MERLIN screening map

Responsible organization

MERLIN- Mainstreaming Ecological Restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems in a Landscape context: INnovation, upscaling, and transformation (101036337—MERLIN—H2020-LC- GD-2020)

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Objectives

The Merlin-screening Map tool provides a Europe-wide upscaling strategy for restoring freshwater-related ecosystems. It identifies and prioritises areas where replicating best-practice restoration measures has large potential to restore freshwater ecosystems, particularly focusing on essential ecosystem services, biodiversity targets, and climate change mitigation. For doing so It conducts a Europe-wide screening of restoration needs identifying areas not meeting legally binding by one or both the Habitats and Water Framework Directives; and a Europe-wide screening of restoration potential, identifying areas with higher provision of ES co-benefits when restoring, easiness of restoration actions implementation and with legal commitments to ecological targets.

The Merlin-screening Map tool uses the River Restoration Units (R2U) resolution, which divides each sea outlet basin into a set of river units with no upstream dependencies that aggregate small watercourses (hereafter, small river units), connected by river units encompassing the mainstem watercourses of the basin (hereafter, large river units).

Key parameters and attributes

	Parameters	Attributes
<i>Mapping Restoration Needs</i>	Detailed composite indicator of conservation status for freshwater-related habitats in River Restoration Units	The Composite Indicator of Conservation Status (ciCS) methodology developed by Carrao et al. (2020b) was followed using data from article 17 of the Habitats Directive. The ciCS aggregates the individual conservation status of multiple elements coexisting in the same unit into one categorical value of conservation status (Carrao et al., 2020b). The method establishes 15 possible categorical values (detailed option) nested into three 3 groups (aggregated option) – Very Low, Low and High – that in general express the dominant CS from U2 to U1 to Fv, respectively. Whenever the “Unknow” CS class is dominant in an R2U, the overall result of the ciCS was termed as “Unclassified”.
	Detailed composite indicator of conservation status for freshwater-related species in River Restoration Units	
	Integration of conservation status of freshwater-related protected Habitats and Species under the Habitats Directive in River Restoration Units	
	Detailed composite indicator of conservation status of Water Framework Directive Good Ecological Status	Using modelled probability of achieving a Good Ecological Status, sensu Water Framework Directive, following Vigiak et al., 2021 methodology.
	Restoration Needs	The combination of the aggregated composite indicator for both the protected freshwater-related habitats and species) and the aggregated composite indicator of the Water Framework Directive Good Ecological Status.
<i>Mapping Restoration Potential</i>	Ecosystem Services Assessment Indicator (ESA)	ESA uses: 1. The Crop Pollination Supply 2. Water Purification Demand 3. The Flood Control Unmet Demand 4. The Soil Retention Unmet Demand 5. The Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) saturation capacity 6. The Nature-based recreation Unmet Demand
	Constraints to Restoration	The Human Footprint Index as the cumulative human pressure on the environment
	Enablers to Restoration	The percentage of Nature Protected Areas within floodplains, outside of floodplains, but within wetlands

Parameters	Attributes
Restoration Potential Index	Restoration Potential Indicator (RPI) values result from the integration of the Ecosystem Services co-benefits, the restoration constraints and the restoration enablers. RPI expresses the easiness of implementing restoration actions and the potential to obtain ES co-benefits from these actions.
<i>Integration of Restoration Needs and Potential</i> Ranked Restoration Potential in River Restoration Units with Restoration Needs	The Restoration Potential Index (RPI) has been ranked and classified using the quantile classification method with 5 classes. Crossing the restoration needs with the rank of RPI values allows the ranking of the areas throughout Europe where restoration needs are present and also determines their restoration potential. This allows for the prioritisation of areas in need of restoration by their upside in terms of potential benefits for both nature and society.
Ecosystem Services Assessment Indicator– Restoration Needs	Integration between the restoration needs and a) the Ecosystem Services Assessment Indicator for each River Restoration Unit, b) the Human Footprint Index (HFI), and c) the enablers to restoration. Restoration Needs classes: "Full Needs" – not abiding by both directives (WFD, HD); "Partial Needs" – not abiding just by one directive; "Partial Needs & Partial Compliance" – a mixed situation of abiding by one directive and not abiding by the other. Higher values indicate areas with higher coverage of protected areas.
Human Footprint Index- Restoration Needs	
Enablers to Restoration -Restoration Needs	

Input datasets

- River Restoration Units (R2U) developed under MERLIN project (available online in <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202501.1142/v1>)

Restoration Needs

Habitats Directive data:

– Article 17 Web Tool. 2022. Article 17 Web Tool. [online] Available at: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-bd/activities/reporting/article-17>> [Accessed 31 March 2022].

Water Framework Directive data:

– Vigiak, Olga; Udias Moinelo, Angel; Pistocchi, Alberto; Zanni, Michela; Aloe, Alberto; Grizzetti, Bruna (2021): European River conditions: probability of failing to achieve good ecological status, or being impacted by nutrient and organic pollution (v. 1.0). European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/35781807-e6c9-4c91-bbff-debd95f612e2>

Methodology:

– Carrao, Hugo, Stefan Kleeschulte, Marco Trombetti, Dania Abdul Malak, Fernando Santos Martín, Adrián García Bruzón, Aurélien Carré, and Sophie Condé. Task 1.7.5.3: Green Infrastructure (Gi). Key Deliverable Kd2 – Green Infrastructure Analysis: Contribution to Wetlands. Vienna, Austria: European Topic Centre on Urban, Land and Soil Systems, 2020.

– Carrao, Hugo, Stefan Kleeschulte, Sandra Naumann, McKenna Davis, Christoph Schröder, Dania Abdul Malak, and Sophie Conde. Contributions to Building a Coherent Trans-European Nature Network. What Is the Contribution of Gi to Improving the Conservation Status of Species of Community Interest and the Delivery of Ecosystem Services in Europe? Strengthening the Gi Network with a View to Enhance Its Multiple Benefits. Vienna, Austria: European Topic Centre on Urban, Land and Soil Systems, 2020.

Restoration Potential

Ecosystem Services data:

– <https://ecosystem-accounts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

– <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-organic-carbon-saturation-capacity>

– Lugato, E., Panagos, P., Bampa, F., Jones, A., Montanarella, L. A new baseline of organic carbon stock in European agricultural soils using a modelling approach (2014a) *Global Change Biology*, 20 (1), pp. 313-326.

– Lugato, E., Bampa, F., Panagos, P., Montanarella, L., Jones, A. Potential carbon sequestration of European arable soils estimated by modelling a comprehensive set of management practices (2014b) *Global Change Biology*, 20 (11), pp. 3557-3567.

Global Human Footprint data:

– <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/set/wildareas-v2-human-footprint-geographic/metadata>

– Wildlife Conservation Society - WCS, and Center for International Earth Science Information Network
– CIESIN – Columbia University. 2005. Last of the Wild Project, Version 2, 2005 (LWP-2): Global Human Footprint Dataset (Geographic). Palisades, New York: NASA Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC). <https://doi.org/10.7927/H4M61H5F>.

Floodplain data:

– Dottori, Francesco; Alfieri, Lorenzo; Bianchi, Alessandra; Skoien, Jon; Salamon, Peter (2021): River flood hazard maps for Europe and the Mediterranean Basin region. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] doi: 10.2905/1D128B6C-A4EE-4858-9E34-6210707F3C81 PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/1d128b6c-a4ee-4858-9e34-6210707f3c81>

Nature 2000 data:

– EEA under the framework of the Copernicus programme, JNCC, JCR

– <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/uk-protected-area-datasets-for-download/>

Maps

Figure 11 – Map showing the detailed composite indicator of Conservation Status class for the protected freshwater-related habitats calculated for River Restoration Units (R2Us) more than 50% within EU Member States. Detailed ciCS: Very low (reds); Low (yellows); High (greens).

Figure 12 – Map showing the detailed composite indicator of Conservation Status class for the protected freshwater-related species calculated for River Restoration Units (R2Us) more than 50% within EU Member States. Detailed ciCS: Very low (reds); Low (yellows); High (greens).

Figure 13 – Map detailing for River Restoration Units (R2Us) integration outcome of the aggregated composite indicator for the protected freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

Figure 14 – Map showing each River Restoration Unit (R2Us) class of the detailed composite indicator of Conservation Status using the modelled probability of achieving a Good Ecological Status, sensu Water Framework Directive. Detailed ciCS: Very low (reds); Low (yellows); High (greens).

Figure 15 – Map showing each River Restoration Unit (R2U) simplified reclassification of the integration outcome based on the integration output of the Habitats Directive (achieved by combining the aggregated composite indicator for both the protected freshwater-related habitats and species) and the aggregated composite indicator of the Water Framework Directive Good Ecological Status. "Full Compliance" means abiding by both directives; "Partial compliance" means abiding by only one directive; "Partial Needs + Partial Compliance" means abiding by one directive and not abiding by the other, "Partial needs" means not abiding by only one directive; "Full Needs" means not abiding by both directives,) and "Unknown" refers to units with unclassified Habitats Directive status and/or uncertain status concerning the Water Framework Directive.

Figure 16 –Ecosystem Services (ES) Assessment Indicator for each River Restoration Unit (R2U). Values were obtained by summing the values established in each R2U for all ES and dividing by the number of ES present.

Figure 17 – Average Human Footprint Index values for each River Restoration Unit (R2U), as a proxy for constraints to restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems. Values close to 1 represent highly human-influenced areas.

Figure 18 – Percentage of the area covered by Restoration Enablers in River Restoration Units (R2U) (0-yellow to 100- dark green). Restoration enablers’ areas are composed of floodplain areas included in the Natura 2000 network of protected sites (N2000) and wetland areas outside floodplains also included in the N2000. The floodplain areas of R2Us were established based on the 500-year flood return period.

Figure 19 –Restoration Potential Index for River Restoration Units (R2Us) (low-red to high-dark green). Values reflect the integration of the Ecosystem Services Assessment Indicator, the indicator of Restoration Constraints, and the indicator of Restoration Enablers. Higher RPI values indicate a higher potential of ecosystem services co-benefits, easiness of implementing restoration actions, and the presence of legal commitment.

Figure 20 –Restoration Potential Index ranked values with the areas of Restoration Needs. Darker blue colours represent the areas in need of restoration that should be prioritised according to their restoration potential.

Figure 21 – Integration of restoration needs and Restoration Potential Index (RPI) for each River Restoration Unit (R2U). Restoration Needs classes: “Partial Needs + Partial Compliance” –a mixed situation of abiding by one directive and not abiding by the other; “Partial needs” – not abiding just by one directive; “Full Needs” – not abiding by both directives. Lower RPI values indicate higher potential co-benefits of Ecosystem Services and easiness of restoration measures implementation.

Figure 22 –Integration of restoration needs and Restoration Constraints (based on the Human Footprint Index – HFI) for each River Restoration Unit. Restoration Needs classes: “Partial Needs + Partial Compliance” –a mixed situation of abiding by one directive and not abiding by the other; “Partial needs” – not abiding just by one directive; “Full Needs” – not abiding by both directives. Lower values of restoration constraints indicate higher easiness of implementation of restoration actions.

Figure 23 –Integration of restoration needs and restoration enablers for each River Restoration Unit. Restoration Needs classes: “Partial Needs + Partial Compliance” – a mixed situation of abiding by one directive and not abiding by the other; “Partial needs” – not abiding just by one directive; “Full Needs” – not abiding by both directives. Higher values of restoration enablers translate to having a higher degree of legal commitment towards freshwater conservation.

Integrated Outputs Proposal

To provide ORP maps integrating several datasets, we presented ORP with an integration rationale that was accepted. The general idea was to show, in RBD (River Basin Districts) of high dam removal opportunity (high DAMROS), which had the highest diversity of freshwater habitats and high diversity of freshwater-dependent species of community interest (sensu Habitats Directive), and only allow the depiction of R2Us (River Restoration Units) with a low probability of failing to achieve “Good Ecological Status” according to the Water Framework Directive. In agreement with ORP, 8 final combinations of integrated outputs were produced to be used according to their needs and funding priorities.

Databases and tools: Important remarks

We decided to use *River Restoration Units (R2Us)* to improve the resolution and allow a more homogeneous spatial data aggregation from each database or tool.

We decided to disregard the *Swimways* database, as it only has information for main rivers (328,238 km of European rivers considered, i.e., 13% of the overall network), creating a spatial coverage issue and also because it only focuses on a reduced group of migratory fish species (92 migratory freshwater fish).

Regarding the *DAMROS* database, after considering the different variations of the scores (DAMROS 10, 7, 5 and 4), we believe that using the simplified DAMROS scores with 4 metrics (DAMROS4) would be the most advantageous, since it is the option with the most complete RBD data coverage (Metrics: Barrier density, Extent of barrier under-reporting, Surface waterbody included in a protected area and, Water stress & future flows).

DAMROS4 Variations:

During meetings with ORP, a proposal for maps with different DAMROS4 variations was discussed and agreed upon. The objective was to highlight areas with Good Ecological Status, using DAMROS4 as a reliable and valued metric to determine the best restoration potential.

Using a bivariate choropleth diamond symbology, these maps display River Restoration Units (R2Us) within selected River Basin Districts (RBD) coloured by the number of freshwater-related species and habitats (Habitats Directive) (Fig.24a).

There are two groups of maps: 1) only showing R2U where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 40% (only showing R2U with GES); 2) only showing R2U where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 60% (only showing R2U with GES, but a bit more permissive). For each of the 2 groups defined above we filtered the data according to DAMROS4 values and created 4 maps: 1) only representing the R2Us within RBDs with a DAMROS 4 score in the 1st (top) quartile; 2) only representing the River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the 1st and 2nd (top) quartiles; 3) only representing the 50 top River Basin Districts (RBD) DAMROS 4 scores; 4) only representing the 100 top River Basin Districts (RBD) DAMROS 4 scores (Fig.24 b).

All maps are available online using the WebMap links in each figure and listed in the section below (WebMap online display example in Fig. 25).

Figure 24 – A) Bivariate choropleth symbology used to represent the number of freshwater-related species and habitats (Habitats Directive) in River Restoration Units (R2Us) (Both high- dark blue; Both low- light yellow; High number of species and Low number of habitats- yellow; High number of habitats and Low number of species- turquoise); B) Grouping of the maps proposed, filtered by Probability of Failing Good Ecological Status (<40% and <60%) and by DAMROS4 value.

Figure 25- Example of WebMap online display of the proposed DAMROS4 variations maps. Using this tool, it is possible to interact with the maps, zoom in and out on relevant areas, select R2Us or river basins and consult the data tables.

Maps

Figure 26– River Restoration Units (R2Us) in River Basin Districts (RBD) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 40% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the 1st (top) quartile, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.
(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=efbaca7a9f97464687757e5034c8e455>)

Figure 27 – River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 40% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the 1st and 2nd (top) quartiles, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=d9b6cbfeb9fe47b4919d056337400198>)

Figure 28- River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 40% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the top 50, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=5866590834cc456db1c5c96d210ff315>)

Figure 29- River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 40% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the top 100, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=0f115c63dba34bca929fd5f80d531ab6>)

Figure 30- River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 60% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the 1st (top) quartile, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=13035a60cb0e4adaab22ccf18d4fc72a>)

Figure 31 – River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 60% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the 1st and 2nd (top) quartiles, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=c30010b0b53f4f1ab177439c20797880>)

Figure 32 — River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 60% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the top 50, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=55cc1a7b99354e57945e22adce2fd73f>)

Figure 33- River Restoration Units (R2Us) where the probability of failing to achieve the “Good Ecological Status” (GES - sensu Water Framework Directive) is equal or lower than 60% (only showing R2U with GES) in River Basin Districts (RBD) with a DAMROS 4 score in the top 100, coloured by the number of freshwater-related habitats and species using a bivariate choropleth map.

(WebMap: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=33ddb55d810245188e9065a5ebc5ef16>)